

Ezenwanyi Ritual among the Igbo People of Nigeria

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Ezenwanyi ritual is associated with the Igbo people of Nigeria. Ezenwanyi is made up of Eze (King) and Nwanyi (Female/Woman). It literally means king woman or woman king. This cult is ancient in some Igbo culture such as Orlu in Imo state and Izzi in Ebonyi state. The wave of cultural revival or going back to our root championed by some contemporary Igbo youths led to emergency of Ezenwanyi cult in some other parts of Igbo communities. Members of this cult averred that they have their root/link to the marine world. Both married and unmarried females belong to the cult. The research revealed that it is by inheritance or calling that one can become an Ezenwanyi. Initiation is performed on the prospective members. Shrines are built and dedicated for the person where rituals are carried out for those consulting her. There is procession into the community to announce the initiation of a new member. Ezenwanyi claims to be the representative of the marine world and acts as a healer. Rituals are performed for people that consult them. There are no specific materials for rituals. It depends on what one is expecting from the goddess. Materials for rituals range from local fowls, goats, sheep, cow, money or even money. Ritual materials that may be difficult for those consulting Ezenwanyi to get are paid for and provided by Ezenwanyi. It is on this premise that exorbitant charge may be demanded by Ezenwanyi. Ezenwanyi is prohibited from attending every occasion, and when she attends receives special recognition as she is not expected to mingle with ordinary people during the occasion. Some of the members of Ezenwanyi cult have been accused of exploiting people, immorality and creating discord in families. It has also been observed that some females are attracted to the cult because of fame, wealth and power associated with Ezenwanyi.

Date Range: 1800 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Igboland, South East, Nigeria

Region tags: Add the map for me using the map of Southeastern Nigeria

five eastern states of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo in Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

– Yes

Notes: Some rituals begin in the shrine and end in road junction, river/stream and forest/groove.

↳ Enclosed?

– No

Notes: The process may begin in enclosed shrine, but ends in the open place.

↳ Elevated?

– No

Notes: It is not statutory for the ritual by Ezenwanyi to be carried out on an elevated platform/site.

↳ By a body of water?

– Yes

Notes: While some rituals are completed beside/ inside river/stream, some end in the groove or road junction.

↳ Near fire (e.g., volcano, lava, human-made fire)?

– No

↳ In a location considered holy?

– No

Notes: Sometimes, the place may not be considered holy but has spiritual connotation.

↳ Other [Specify]

– N/A

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting?

– No

Notes: Rituals are done in the shrine and may continue at the road junction or water side.

Is the ritual carried out in a public place?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual carried out in public place such as road junction is done in middle of night or very early in the morning. People wake up only to discover that ritual has been performed on the road junction.

↳ Is the public space restricted in any way? (i.e. public, but only for specific members of the religious group?)

– I Don't Know

Is the ritual carried out in a private place?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual is carried out both in public and private places. Sometimes, ritual materials after the ritual can be placed in road junction in hour of the night as may be instructed by the Ezenwanyi to the participants.

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Shrines are built by the ezenwanyi for the purpose of ritual.

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

– Yes

Notes: Some places are considered sacred while some places such as road junction may not be considered sacred but is believed to have link with the spiritual world.

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

– Yes

Notes: The sites are created but considered as sacred.

↳ Was it temporary?

– No

Notes: The places for ritual are usually put in place by humans. They are not intended to serve temporary purposes.

↳ Was it permanent?

– Yes

Notes: So long the shrine exists and receives rituals, it remains. Ritual sites are not meant to be temporary sites.

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

– Yes

Notes: The sites are human creation associated with divine approval.

↳ Through divination:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that the site location is concluded on by supernatural directives sometimes through divination.

↳ Through astronomical observation:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Through myths, legends or literature:

– Yes

Notes: Myth and legends play vital role in Igbo culture. This may be the reason for sitting some shrine where they are located.

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

– Yes

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

– I Don't Know

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

– No

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

– I Don't Know

Notes: However, Eastern direction is vital in the eastern Nigeria because sun rises in the east.

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

– No

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

– Yes

↳ Annually:

– Yes

Notes: Some rituals are done annually.

↳ Daily:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals are done whenever someone consults the ezenwanyi.

↳ Weekly:

– Yes

Notes: There four market day (orie, Afo, Nkwo, Eke) that make up traditional week. Some of the Ezenwanyi maintain some days for rituals.

↳ Seasonally:

– Yes

Notes: Seasons are important aspect of tradition in Igbo culture.

↳ Once in an individual's lifetime:

– No

↳ Special events/occasions:

– No

↳ During life cycle events (marriage, birth, death, etc.):

– No

↳ Ad hoc:

– No

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified?

– Yes

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours)

– No

Notes: What determines duration is the ritual being carried out.

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual?

def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual

– Yes

↳ How many agents are involved in this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no strict rules regarding the actual number of agents involved in any ritual conducted by the Ezenwanyi. She is usually a constant figure in any ritual conducted under her authority/supervision. Material facts or situations surrounding any ritual will determine the number of individuals/agents who will join her in any ritual.

↳ Are agents of specific gender/sex for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they male:

– No

↳ Are they female:

– Yes

↳ Are they transgender:

– No

↳ Are they non-binary:

– No

↳ Are they other:

– No

↳ What is the age range of agents in this ritual?

– N/A

↳ Do agents have to have biological distinctiveness for this ritual?

(e.g., twin, born breach, albino, mental illness, hermaphrodite, blind, other disability)

– No

↳ Do agents have to have a specific social role for this ritual?

(e.g., widow, unmarried, etc.)

– No

↳ Are agents required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are agents initiated?

– Yes

↳ Are agents part of the social group?

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Are agents required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: There is no requirement for agents to be outsiders in rituals conducted/supervised by the Ezenwanyi

↳ Are agents required to be specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: It is only those initiated into and occupying the office of Ezenwanyi.

↳ Are agents non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for agents in this ritual?

(e.g., menstruating women, men of a certain age)

– None

↳ Are there supernatural agents associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are deeply involved in the social engineering of the Igbo culture and so are natural participants or recipients of ritual and other cultural practices.

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are involved in this form of rituals.

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– Yes

↳ Are they animals:

– No

↳ Are they plants:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– No

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– No

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

Definition: humans who have undergone deliberate efforts to

change/refine/develop/transform themselves.

– No

↳ Other:

–Specify: They are ancestors

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

– Yes

↳ Is the patient the same as the agent of the ritual?

– No

↳ Is the patient absent from the ritual?

– No

Notes: The patient is expected to be present.

↳ Is the patient present during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is the patient physically present?

– Yes

↳ Is the patient virtually present?

– No

↳ How many patients are required for the ritual to take place?

–Yes: 1

Notes: At least one patient is enough for the ritual to take place

↳ Do patients have to be of a specific gender/sex for the purpose of this ritual?

– No

↳ What is the age range of patients in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: There is no specific age.

↳ Do patients have to have a specific social role for this ritual?

– No

Notes: The minimum patients need to do is to be present at the ritual and follow the Ezenwanyi (ritual agent's) instructions and advice at all times.

↳ Are patients required to be insiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are patients required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Most of the time, patients are outsiders for the rituals to take place. They are often those seeking help or intervention in one area of their lives or the other.

↳ Are patients required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are patients non-specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for patients in this ritual?

– Yes [specify]: Patients should not be disobey the advice of the Ezenwanyi because they could have very grave consequences. or

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as patients in this ritual?

– No

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?

– N/A

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:

– Yes

↳ Male:

– Yes

↳ Female:

– Yes

↳ Transgender:

– No

↳ Non-binary:

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: The age range is not specified. Any individual with a need to consult the Ezenwanyi is allowed to do so. Therefore, there are no age limits to those who may consult the specialist for support or assistance.

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?
– No

Notes: Participants are not required to be insiders for this ritual to take place.

↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual?
– Yes

Notes: Most of the time, participants are outsiders to the ritual. They approach the specialist with their issues and solutions are sought as the specialist deems fit.

↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual?
– Yes

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual?
– Yes [specify]: They have to listen to instructions and follow the leading of the supernatural agents being consulted.

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual?
– No

Are there spectators in this ritual?

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

– Yes

↳ How many spectators observe this ritual?

– I Don't Know

↳ The spectators' gender/sex is:

– Yes

↳ Male:

– Yes

↳ Female:

– Yes

↳ Transgender:

– No

↳ Non-binary:

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ What is the age range of spectators in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Do spectators have a specific social role for this ritual?

– No

Notes: They are only present anticipating the success of the ritual and to show support and

solidarity to the specialist and patient alike.

→ Are spectators required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Spectators could be insiders supporting the ritual specialist or outsiders in solidarity with the patient and their loved ones.

→ Are spectators required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– Yes

→ Are spectators required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Spectators could both be specialists or non-specialists as the case may be.

→ Are spectators non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

→ Are there specific prohibitions for spectators to take part in this ritual?

– Yes [specify]: They must not disrupt the proceedings and always show respect to the specialists and the ritual process being carried out.

→ Are there supernatural beings that act as spectators in this ritual?

– No

Cause/Trigger

Is this ritual practiced at will?

– Yes

Notes: This ritual does not have season. It is performed when one thinks it is necessary.

→ Is it individually determined:

– Yes

Notes: An individual determines when it is important to perform the ritual.

↳ Is it communally determined:

– No

Notes: But few individuals can claim to have performed ritual on behalf of the community.

Is participation obligatory?

– Yes

Notes: It is expected that the people who have asked for the ritual participate. The ritual is performed on their behalf, therefore, their participation is obligatory.

↳ Consequences of non-participation:

– I Don't Know

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual can be part of event of initiating new member into Ezenwanyi cult.

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

– Yes

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death, etc.)?

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Traditionally, ritual is performed when a religious specialist die. Such ritual may be performed.

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, rituals are performed in response to ominous events

↳ Is the omen induced?

– No

↳ Is the omen observed?

– Yes

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

– No

Notes: The rituals are not usually tied to specific life stages. However, when an individual is passing through difficult situations they may consult the Ezenwanyi who prescribes the appropriate rituals to help resolve their challenges.

Is this ritual part of another ritual?

– No

Notes: Any ritual performed by Ezenwanyi is independent of other rituals.

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants?

– Yes

↳ By a government or ruling elite:

– No

↳ By NGOs:

Definition: NGO: Non-profit organization

– No

↳ By clans or families:

– Yes [specify]: This is done as a support, or not to be seen supporting traditional activity.

↳ By particular individuals:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: In Igbo culture, human tries to maintain peaceful relationship with the spiritual world. Some rituals are performed to maintain cordial relationship with the world of the spirit.

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change?

– Yes

Notes: It is challenges of life that pushes human into looking for solution. Ritual is performed as part of the way to look for solution to human problems. Positive results are expected from the rituals.

↳ Is the change expected to be positive:

– Yes

↳ Is the change expected to be negative:

– No

Notes: No one expects to have negative response to his ritual.

↳ Is the change expected to be neutral:

– No

Notes: Neutrality is not positive response, therefore, the ritual is not expected to be neutral.

↳ Select the type of change:

– Political

– Legal

– Social

– Cultural

– Spiritual

– Ecological

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The domains could be spiritual or metaphysical

↳ Is it divine/spiritual:

– Yes

↳ Is it non-human organic entities (e.g., nature, animals, plants):

– No

↳ Is it abiotic/inorganic entities (and objects):

– No

↳ Is it ecological:

– No

↳ Is it transformed humans:

– Yes

↳ Is it for knowledge transmission (e.g., oral storytelling):

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Specific goals are associated with this ritual. Whenever they are performed, it is for a specific goal.

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– Yes

↳ For deceased humans:

– No

↳ For non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ For abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ For divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals are performed to show dependence on the divine /spiritual beings.

↳ Are they high gods:

– No

Notes: They are deities or ancestors

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:
– No

↳ For transformed/self-cultivated humans:
– No

↳ Other:
– N/A

↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual?
– No

↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual?
– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, the Ezenwanyi discovers the causes of crises experienced by patients could be their wrong actions. They therefore seek the forgiveness of the spiritual beings to help reverse the consequences suffered by the patient and their families.

↳ Is domestication of agents a goal?
Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.
– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information?
– Yes

Notes: The ritual is sometimes practiced to obtain information which can not be accessed naturally but through spiritual consultation.

↳ About the future/past/present:
– Yes

↳ General information:

– No

↳ About something specific:

– Yes [specify]: Sometimes specific enquiries are made in the ritual to decipher why somethings are happening in order to find solutions to ugly occurrences.

↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual helps in self appraisal to seek ways of becoming better people so as to avoid negative occurrences in the lives of the patients.

↳ To become god-like:

– No

Notes: Becoming god-like is not an essential goal of this ritual

↳ To become immortal:

– No

Notes: Immortality is not a goal of this ritual

↳ To achieve divine or superhuman attributes:

– No

↳ For salvation/liberation from the world:

– Yes

↳ For spiritual cleansing:

– Yes

Notes: This is one of the major reasons for approaching the Ezenwanyi for ritual performances.

↳ To achieve moral perfection:

– No

Notes: Moral perfection is never a goal for this ritual although generally, Igbo people seek to get better in conduct and character but to attain moral perfection is somewhat difficult to attain.

↳ For an initiation into a new status:

– Yes

↳ To achieve a change in mental state:

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural agents?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual performed for purification?

– Yes

Notes: Purification is a big motivation for this ritual. Purification from evil omen, evil contact and contaminants etc are causes for the conduct of this ritual.

↳ Is it physical:

– Yes

↳ Is it mental:

– Yes

↳ Is it emotional:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes?

– Yes

↳ For expelling spirits:

– Yes

Notes: The rituals are carried out to expel evil spirits

↳ For summoning spirits:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits are often summoned for assistance, support and intervention during the rituals.

↳ For gaining special knowledge from spirits:

– Yes

Notes: The occasion of the rituals also serve the purpose of helping the specialists and patients gain special knowledge about the challenges they face from the spirits.

↳ For spiritual communication:

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes?

– Yes

↳ During a specific illness?

– Yes

↳ Is it physical:

– Yes

↳ Is it psychological:

– Yes

↳ Is it emotional:

– Yes

↳ Is it social:

– No

↳ Is it cultural:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes when an individual, a family or clan has abandoned their obligations to the deities, they face difficult situations. When they consult the Ezenwanyi, the spirits may reveal to the specialists that the patients are suffering from the consequences of abandoning their cultural obligations. When they seek forgiveness and change their ways, they most often find relief.

↳ Is it sexual:

– No

↳ Is it energetic:

– No

↳ is it environmental:

– No

↳ Is it spiritual:

– Yes

↳ During anxiety:
– Yes

↳ During depression:
– No

– Yes

↳ During an injury?
– Yes

↳ Is it physical:
– Yes

↳ Is it psychological:
– Yes

↳ Is it spiritual:
– Yes

↳ To improve fertility?
– Yes

↳ To achieve longevity?
– Yes

↳ To support development/growth?
– I Don't Know

↳ To achieve vitality?

– Yes

↳ To improve virility?

– Yes

↳ To achieve resurrection?

– No

Notes: Resurrection is not the goal of the indigenous belief system of the igbo people

↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual makes the Ezenwanyi to transmit information and also to receive information from the marine world.

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)?

– Yes

↳ Is this a naming ritual?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm?

– No

Notes: This ritual has nothing to do with the practice of inflicting harm

↳ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes?

– Yes

Notes: Ezenwanyi rituals are many times performed for protection purposes. They are held to be effective in protection against injury, harm, losses, for the community to be in peace etc

↳ Against spells/witchcraft:

– Yes

↳ To avoid illness:

– Yes

↳ To avoid injury:

– Yes

↳ For a safe pregnancy:

– Yes

↳ For children:

– Yes

↳ To avoid discovery:

– No

↳ Against weapons:

– Yes

↳ To avoid vices (temptation):

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)?

– No

- ↳ Is this ritual associated with infanticide?
 - No

- ↳ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance?
 - No

- ↳ Is this ritual associated with travel?
 - I Don't Know

- ↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations?
 - No

- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success?
 - Yes
 - ↳ For professional success (e.g., exam, promotion):
 - Yes

 - ↳ For legal success:
 - Yes

 - ↳ To obtain income/wealth:
 - Yes

 - ↳ To escape debt:
 - I Don't Know

 - ↳ For business success:
 - Yes

↳ To recover lost objects:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

Is the causal efficacy assessed?

– Yes

Notes: The Igbo cultural group believes the ritual is efficacious to bring about definite and far reaching occurrences in the lives of patients and anyone who seeks the assistance of the ancestors through the ritual performers (Ezenwanyi)

↳ Concrete outcomes in the world:

– Yes

↳ Further ritual checks:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

Notes: The efficacy of the ritual is expected to be experienced through positive response to their requests.

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Sound is part of the ritual.

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community?

– No

Notes: The sound may or may not be organized. Therefore, the sound does not have to be music exclusively

in the local culture.

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

– Yes

↳ Is it oral?

– Yes

↳ Is it communal? (e.g., choir)

– No

↳ Is it individual?

– Yes

Notes: The sounds are either made by the ritual specialist or the patients/spectators. They are usually to achieve a goal related to the ritual.

↳ Is there a call and response?

– Yes

↳ It involves singing:

– Yes

↳ It involves chanting:

– Yes

↳ it involves invocation/prayer:

– Yes

↳ It involves mantras:

– I Don't Know

↳ It involves wailing/cheering (heightened emotional expression):

– No

Notes: This is not a usual component or occurrence in the ritual but may happen as a result of specific experiences of the ritual performer and or the patient(s)/spectator(s).

↳ It involves narrative/recitation:

– Yes

Notes: This may happen depending on the specific situations surrounding a particular ritual involving an individual. The situations surrounding each individual determines whether or not narravits or recitations will take place.

↳ It involves whistling:

– Yes

↳ It involves shouting/loud vocalizations:

– No

↳ Is the sound produced with parts of the body?

– Yes

Notes: Speeches made by the ritual specialists are types of sounds produced during the ritual. Prayers, invocation, enquiries, responses from the patient are parts of sounds produced during the ritual.

↳ Does the sound involve hand movement?

– Yes

Notes: The form of hand movement usually witnessed during the rituals include non-verbal communication, gesticulations etc

↳ Does it involve clapping?

– No

Notes: It doesn't usually involve clapping but this is not to rule clapping out completely when they are deemed necessary. .

↳ Does it involve body concussion?

– No

↳ Does the sound involve feet movement?

– No

↳ Are there instruments/objects involved in creating sounds for the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they membranophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating a membrane (e.g., kettle drums, cylindrical drums).

– Yes

↳ Are they idiophone:

Definition: Instruments that create sound through vibrating themselves (e.g., xylophones, jaw's harp).

– Yes

↳ Are they aerophone:

Definition: Instruments that create noise by pushing vibrating columns of air through them (e.g., accordions, pitch pipes, ocarinas, bagpipes).

– No

↳ Are they chordophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating strings (e.g., guitar, violin, harp).

– No

↳ Are they electrophone:

Definition: Instruments where the sound is produced by electric or electronic means (e.g., synthesizers, computers).

– No

↳ Are they architectural features:

def: water channeled in underground canals, fountains, or other architectural features that create sounds for the ritual

– No

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing these instrumental sounds:

– Yes

Notes: A minimum of one person is required to produce the sound.

↳ Is it scripted?

– No

↳ Is it semantic?

– Yes

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– No

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– No

↳ Is it performed by specialists?

– No

↳ Does it require formal training?

– No

Notes: It may require observations and apprenticeship.

↳ Does the sound change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The sound may change depending on the stage of the ritual.

↳ Does the change correlate to the stage of the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is there musical texture in the instrumental sound?

– No

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?

– No

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?

– No

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ The sound is:

– Improvised

Is movement involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual?

– No

↳ Is it coordinated with sound?

– No

↳ Does it involve the use of objects?

– Yes

Notes: Iron gong, local drum and flute are some of the objects used.

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement

– N/A

Notes: The number is not specific.

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific body markings done for the ritual?

– No

Notes: But Ezenwanyi do have body markings.

↳ Is there hair regulation as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve shaving:

– Yes

↳ Does it involve a specific hair style:

– No

↳ Is there tooth modification involved in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are individuals partly or fully naked as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: This may only happen if a segment of the ritual requires that some ritual actions be

performed on the body of the patient.

↳ Are scars made as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Are piercings made as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are objects inserted in the earlobe?

– Yes

↳ Does genital modification take place during this ritual?

– No

↳ Do individuals have to wear specific clothing for this ritual?

– No

Notes: There is no strict prescription about this.

↳ Are there jewelry/charms used during this ritual?

– No

Notes: Charms are not often used except when they are deployed to keep malevolent spirits away from the ritual site or from harming those present at the ritual.

↳ Are masks used during the ritual?

– No

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they totems:

– No

↳ Are they religious icons:

– No

↳ Are they fetishes:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, fetish items could be used during the ritual for spiritual fortification.

↳ Are they vessels:

– Yes

↳ Are they masks:

– No

↳ Are they standards (banner, flag):

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ How are these materials/objects implemented?

– I Don't Know

Notes: They are implemented at the discretion of the ritual agent (Ezenwanyi)

↳ Is text used during this ritual?

– No

↳ Is painting used during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is a technological object used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are plants or plant parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Herbs, bark of trees and plant roots are part of the materials to be used.

↳ Are animals or animal parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Animal is an important material for ritual. It may include: cow, goats, sheep and fowl.

↳ Are human body parts (including flesh) used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are bodily fluids used as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Do topical applications take place during this ritual?

– No

↳ Is water used?

– Yes

Notes: Many of the rituals take place by water bodies and because water is a purifying agent in Igbo culture, the element becomes an important component of the rituals conducted by the Ezenwanyi

↳ Is earth used?

– Yes

Notes: The mere fact that the ritual takes place on the ground which is also an essential element in ritual performance makes the earth an important factor in the ritual performance.

↳ Is a mirror used?

– Yes

↳ Are textiles used?

– Yes

↳ Is fire used?

– Yes

↳ Is it smoke:

– Yes

Notes: While fire is a purifying agent in Igbo culture, smoke is used many times to cleanse, ward off evil spirits and as conveyors of sacrifices to the deities who are believed to inhabit the sky and other strategic spaces/places in the natural environment. Smoke therefore serves as a conveyor belt to transport the requests, prayers and petitions to the deities for their actions

↳ Is it incense:

– Yes

↳ Is it candle(s):

– Yes

↳ Is it torch(es):

– Yes

Notes: If parts of the rituals are carried out in the night, torches might be needed where it is allowed

↳ Is it burnt objects like paper, leaves, or wood:

– No

Notes: Except when wood is being burnt to provide light at night or to prepare local herbs and concoctions for the use of the patients.

↳ Is it a large fire:

– No

↳ Is there interaction with ritual material during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it passed around?

– No

↳ Is it kissed?

– No

↳ Is it placed somewhere specifically?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual materials are usually kept in specific places where they would be picked up for use when the time is ripe

↳ Is it processed to create something else?

– No

↳ Is it touched?

– Yes

↳ Is it used to touch?

– I Don't Know

Notes: Some ritual items are used to touch the patients to activate some intended actions, results or healing while the ritual is ongoing.

↳ Is it altered during the course of the ritual?

– No

↳ Is it worn?

– Yes

Notes: Some ritual items are worn for the purpose of effecting desired results or outcomes

↳ Is it used to maintain a boundary?

– Yes

Notes: Some ritual items are placed in some specific places to maintain ritual boundaries. These include curtains or clothes used to demarcate the shrine so non-initiates do not pry into the inner recesses of the shrine as this could have grave consequences on them and their wellbeing.

↳ Is it placed at a specific physical distance?

– Yes

↳ Is it close?

– No

Notes: No specific distance is to be maintained. The distance is the decision of the Ezenwanyi in consideration of the safety of everyone.

↳ Is it far?

– No

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals participate in consumption?

– N/A

Notes: The number of people involved in consumption depends on the number of people present during the ritual

↳ Is food consumed?

– Yes

↳ Is it human:

Definition: this can include by fire, natural features of landscape

– No

↳ Is it a non-human animal:

– Yes

↳ Is it a plant:

– Yes

↳ Is it a fungus:

– No

↳ Is this food restricted to the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, the food consumed during the ritual may be restricted to the ritual.

↳ Is the preparation of the food ritualized?

– Yes

↳ Is the presentation of the food ritualized?

– Yes

↳ In what state is the food consumed?

– Cooked

↳ Is a non-normative portion (excessive or deficient) served?

– No

↳ Is it sacralized food?

– Yes

↳ Is it symbolic food?

e.g., standing in for another food or substance or metaphysical concept

– Yes

↳ Is the food consumed associated with healing powers?

– Yes

↳ Does food consumption happen on site?

– Yes

↳ Does the food consumption happen off site?

– No

↳ Does the ritual take place before food consumption?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual would have taken place then the food consumption follows. The food is in many cases expected to serve as a follow-up medication to the ritual which is the spiritual exercise

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the supernatural source of the food?

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, the Ezenwanyi or other ritual specialists are convinced the food was either cooked or breathed upon by the deities/ancestors who will then energise it to achieve the purpose intended in the body or the life of the patient.

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the environmental source of the food?

– Yes

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the (human) provider of the food?

– Yes

↳ Does the ritual encourage sustainable eating behavior?

– Yes

↳ Reducing wastefulness:

– Yes

↳ Mindful eating:

– Yes

↳ Vegetarianism:

– No

Notes: This is not always the goal of the consumption of food after a ritual. This can be buttressed by the fact that meat usually forms part of the ritual meal.

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Are there specific types of consumption that are forbidden?

– I Don't Know

↳ Is a psychoactive substance used in this ritual?

– No

↳ How is the substance used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: This is the exclusive preserve of the ritual specialists

↳ Are other substances used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they charms:

– Yes

Notes: Only the ritual specialists know the nature of many items used in the ritual. Non-initiates may be able to identify the physical components of certain items but cannot tell whether or not those natural/physical elements have been energised by spiritual/esoteric methods.

↳ Are they inorganic minerals:

– I Don't Know

Notes: Powder, local chalks are used but their physical/chemical components cannot be determined unless subjected to proper analysis..

↳ Is the substance shared from a communal vessel or implement?

– No

Notes: The ritual specialists have the discretion to determine where the ritual food or other items would be kept or served.

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness?

– No

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings non-material?

– No

↳ Are the offerings material?

– Yes

↳ Are they consumed by the ritual participants?

– Yes

Notes: Some part of the offerings are consumed by the ritual specialists while some are offered as sacrifices or poured out as libation to the gods and ancestors.

↳ Are the offerings symbolic?

– Yes

↳ Is there a substitution used to represent the symbolic offerings?

– No

↳ Do offerings serve as payments for the ritual specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are animals offered?

– Yes

↳ Is the whole animal offered?

– Yes

↳ How many animals are offered?

– N/A

Notes: The number or species of animals offered depends on the nature of the ritual to be conducted. The final decision on this comes from the ritual specialists.

↳ Is part of the animal offered?

– Yes

↳ How many parts of the animals are offered?

– N/A

Notes: The part or portion of the animal offered depends on the type of ritual been

performed.

↳ Are the animals domestic?

– Yes

↳ How many domestic?

– N/A

Notes: Notes: The number of animals offered is determined by the type of ritual been performed.

↳ Are they wild animals?

– No

↳ Are humans offered?

– No

↳ Is food offered for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are specific drinks offered for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Local gin is the most accepted drink.

↳ Are psychoactive substances offered?

– No

↳ Are commodities offered?

– Yes

↳ Are household items offered?

– Yes

↳ Are personal items offered?

– Yes

Notes: Someone can offer personal items.

↳ Is clothing offered?

– Yes

↳ Are musical instrument offered?

– No

↳ Are texts offered?

– No

↳ Are weapons offered?

– No

↳ Is money (or other valuable items) offered?

– Yes

↳ Are precious substances offered?

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual?

– No

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is sufficient enough to stand on itself.

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals?

– No

Notes: Sometimes, it could be one of some other prescriptions made by the specialists to complete a full circle spiritual interventions needed for a patient to achieve wholeness.

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?

– Yes

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?

– No

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?

– Medium

Notes: The level of repetition is not determined. It is based on leading of the Ezenwanyi.

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

– Medium

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

– Medium

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

– High

Is there behavioral conformity?

– No

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the roles differentiated?

– Yes

Notes: The roles of the Ezenwanyi priest differs from those of the patient during a ritual.

Is there entrainment in this ritual?

– No

Notes: The ritual is solely to the marine world. In most cases, rituals are dropped at designated places or thrown in river/stream.

Is there coordination in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: It is the Ezenwanyi that coordinates. Movement is organized because process of ritual is seen to be solemn.

↳ What is the level of coordination?

– High

Notes: High level of coordination is maintained to enable the spiritual world accept the ritual.

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

Notes: The Ezenwanyi coordinates the movement and sound and draws the attention of the people when necessary.

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: There is time needed to prepare both on the part of the Ezenwanyi priest and the patients to ensure the ritual makes its mark and achieves its purpose.

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation?

– N/A

Notes: There is no specific hours.

Are there preparation activities involved?

– Yes

Notes: There are preparation required. During the menstrual cycle, Ezenwanyi is prohibited from performing rituals.

↳ Does it involve fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, it involves fasting for food and sex.

↳ Does it involve purification:

– Yes

Notes: It is required of Ezenwanyi to purify her self after menstrual cycle.

↳ Does it involve learning/training:

– Yes

Notes: For those being initiated as new members of the cult.

↳ Does it involve penance:

– Yes

↳ Does it involve abstention:

– Yes [specify]: Sometimes, the ritual requires abstention from certain substances like food, sex etc

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Only those initiated are qualified to carry out the ritual.

What is the level of expertise required?

– High

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual?

– No

Notes: The level of economic cost for each ritual is determined by how elaborate or simple the ritual is

What is the transmission mode of the ritual?

– Vertical

– Horizontal

– Esoteric

How is the ritual transmitted?

– In oral form

Who or what has authority over this ritual?

– Divine beings

– Religious specialists

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